

Marketing

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**Strategic approaches to utilizing influencer marketing for scaling small
businesses**

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Abstract. The study's relevance is due to the need for small businesses to adapt to the new realities of the digital market, where traditional advertising tools are losing effectiveness, but trust in influencers as promotion channels is rapidly growing. In today's information environment, influencer marketing creates opportunities for building authentic communication with target audiences, which is particularly valuable for businesses with limited resources. However, the absence of unified strategies and a clear understanding of collaboration specifics complicates its strategic implementation. The **article aims** to provide a theoretical justification and empirical analysis of strategic approaches to using influencer marketing to scale small businesses, considering digital trends, consumer behavior, and the specifics of entrepreneurial resources. The **methodology** is based on a qualitative analysis of case studies of Ukrainian small businesses, content analysis of digital communications, and systematization of practical collaboration models with influencers. A comparative interpretation of practices across different stages of

business development and marketing objectives was conducted. **Results** show that the success of influencer collaboration in small businesses is determined by audience reach, audience relevance, brand-value alignment, and the adaptability of collaboration formats to resource constraints. It was revealed that cooperation models should align with the business growth phase - from unpaid partnerships with thought leaders to structured contractual cooperation with professional influencers. **Conclusions** indicate the necessity of sequential planning of influencer campaigns, considering barriers such as limited resources, reputational risks, and lack of tailored performance indicators. It was demonstrated that strategic cooperation is possible when brand and influencer values are aligned, and a flexible approach to collaboration formats is adopted. Prospects for further research include the development of strategic planning tools for influencer marketing tailored to the industry specifics of small businesses, as well as the study of cultural factors in cooperation with micro- and macro-influencers within the Ukrainian market context.

Keywords: digital communication, brand awareness, consumer behavior, opinion leader engagement, marketing adaptation, content trust.

Стратегічні підходи до використання інфлюенсер-маркетингу для масштабування малого бізнесу

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Анотація. Актуальність дослідження зумовлено необхідністю адаптації малих підприємств до нових реалій цифрового ринку, де традиційні рекламні інструменти втрачають ефективність, а довіра до інфлюенсерів як каналів

просування стрімко зростає. У сучасному інформаційному середовищі інфлюенсер-маркетинг відкриває можливості для побудови автентичної комунікації з аудиторією, що особливо важливо для малого бізнесу з обмеженими ресурсами. Утім, відсутність уніфікованих стратегій і розуміння специфіки такої взаємодії ускладнює її впровадження на практиці. **Мета** статті полягає в теоретичному обґрунтуванні та емпіричному дослідженні стратегічних підходів до використання інфлюенсер-маркетингу як інструменту масштабування малого бізнесу, з урахуванням цифрових тенденцій, поведінки споживачів та специфіки підприємницьких ресурсів. **Методологія** дослідження ґрунтується на поєднанні якісного аналізу кейсів українського малого бізнесу, контент-аналізу цифрових комунікацій та систематизації практичних моделей співпраці з інфлюенсерами. Застосовано порівняльну інтерпретацію практик в межах різних етапів розвитку підприємств і маркетингових завдань. **Результати** дослідження дозволили встановити, що успішність взаємодії з інфлюенсерами у малому бізнесі визначається не лише охопленням аудиторії, а й рівнем її релевантності, відповідністю цінностей бренду та здатністю адаптувати формат співпраці до ресурсних можливостей. Виявлено, що моделі взаємодії мають змінюватися залежно від фази розвитку підприємства: від безоплатного партнерства з лідерами думок до структурованої контрактної співпраці з професійними інфлюенсерами. **Висновки** вказують на необхідність послідовного планування інфлюенсер-кампаній, врахування бар'єрів у вигляді ресурсних обмежень, репутаційних ризиків та відсутності адаптованих індикаторів ефективності. Доведено, що стратегічна співпраця можлива за умови узгодженості цінностей бренду й інфлюенсера та гнучкого підходу до форм взаємодії. Перспективи подальших досліджень передбачають розробку інструментів стратегічного планування інфлюенсер-маркетингу в контексті галузевих особливостей малого бізнесу, а також вивчення культурної

специфіки взаємодії з мікро- та макроінфлюенсерами в умовах українського ринку.

Ключові слова: цифрова комунікація, брендова впізнаваність, поведінка споживачів, взаємодія з лідерами думок, маркетингова адаптація, довіра до контенту.

Problem statement. In today's digital transformation of the business environment, small businesses face challenges related to the need to adapt to new forms of communication with consumers quickly. One of the promising digital marketing tools that opens up opportunities for scaling small businesses with limited resources is influencer marketing. Despite the rapid growth of its popularity, a systematic approach to choosing strategies for interacting with opinion leaders, taking into account the behavioral characteristics of the target audience, product specifics, and the limitations of small businesses, remains insufficiently researched. The problem is that most small businesses use influencer marketing in a fragmented manner, without a formulated long-term strategy, which reduces the effectiveness of campaigns and does not allow for a sustainable increase in the customer base. In scientific terms, this necessitates formalizing criteria for selecting influencers, modeling communication scenarios, and studying factors that affect conversion in conditions of high digital competition. From a practical point of view, developing universal but adaptive strategic models that allow small businesses to effectively integrate influencer marketing into the overall promotion system while ensuring economic feasibility and measurability of results is relevant. In this context, the strategic use of influencers is seen as a means of temporarily increasing brand awareness and a component of a comprehensive marketing ecosystem of small businesses with a long-term impact on their competitiveness.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Analysis of modern research on strategic approaches to influencer marketing for scaling small businesses allows us to identify four main content areas.

The first area focuses on the conceptual foundations of influencer marketing as a component of small businesses' communication and brand-oriented strategy. L. V. Tiesheva and Ye. D. Borysenko [1] investigate the communications problems in organizations, focusing on the role of digital channels and interaction with influencers in building brand trust. The study by L. V. Tiesheva and V. S. Drobitko [2] emphasizes that strategic brand-oriented management is impossible without communication activity in the media space provided by influencers. These works create a basic platform for further developing models of strategic positioning of small businesses in the digital environment. It is advisable to continue research on integrated branding strategies involving influencers.

The second direction covers the influence of influencers on consumer behavior. Yu. Vronska [3] analyzes the transformation of media content of popular Instagram bloggers in the context of war, recording adaptive models of interaction with the audience. I. V. Hvozdetzka and N. V. Hodovaniuk [4] emphasize the role of micro-influencers in consumer decision-making at the local level. A. Strungar [5] distinguishes the benefits and risks of engaging micro- and macro-influencers, showing how the type of influencer affects reach, trust, and spending. Further research in this direction should study the target audience's reaction to different forms of interaction with influencers, in particular from the point of view of cognitive perception and effectiveness of influence.

The third direction is devoted to strategic partnerships between small businesses and influencers. O. Burdiak, L. Pomazan and I. Havryliuk [6] identify key parameters for choosing an influencer: authenticity, frequency of interaction with subscribers and audience segmentation. I. Perevozova, I. S. Zemliakov, G. B. Duda, L. D. Lozinska and V. M. Shaiban [7] consider analytical tools for

assessing the effectiveness of influencer campaigns within the digital marketing framework. O. Horobchenko [8] investigates influencers to scale e-business through direct communication with a potential client. V. V. Bondarchuk, K. V. Shymanska and L. S. Bondarchuk [9] propose an approach to promoting products in social networks with a focus on flexibility, rapid hypothesis testing and visual appeal of content. A promising direction for further research is to model cooperation scenarios between small businesses and influencers at different stages of the company's life cycle.

The fourth direction includes international influencer marketing strategies relevant to small businesses. S. Dimitrieska and T. Efremova [10] indicate that influencers provide a higher level of trust for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) than traditional advertising due to personalized content. S. Cartwright, H. Liu and I. A. Davies [11] demonstrate that even B2B organizations successfully implement influencer marketing, focusing on professional experts. G. G. Glenister [12] formulates a step-by-step strategy for implementing influencer campaigns for SMEs, from blogger selection to ROI assessment. K. Agustian, R. Hidayat, A. Zen, R. A. Sekarini and A. J. Malik [13] show how influencers stimulate sales growth and brand awareness among Southeast Asian SMEs. G. Ye, L. Hudders, S. De Jans and M. De Veirman [14] conduct an in-depth bibliometric analysis and identify promising areas for further research, including automation of influencer selection, ethical dilemmas and cross-media performance measurement. This area requires further development, considering the specifics of the Ukrainian market, particularly in the context of limited resources and an unstable environment.

Thus, the research indicates a high scientific and applied interest in the strategic implementation of influencer marketing in small businesses. Promising areas include the development of integrated strategies for interacting with opinion leaders, assessing the economic efficiency of such solutions, building partnerships

based on trust, and implementing international experience, taking into account the needs of the national market.

Identification of unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite the growing scientific interest in influencer marketing as part of digital strategies, several key aspects that hinder the full implementation of this tool in small businesses remain unresolved. The specifics of the application of influencer marketing in various business models of small businesses have not been sufficiently studied, and there are no generalized approaches to assessing the effectiveness of campaigns taking into account audience coverage, engagement, and relevance indicators. A separate problem is the lack of unified models of interaction between enterprises and influencers depending on the stage of business development, which complicates the adaptation of promotion strategies to the real resource capabilities of entrepreneurs.

Within the framework of this study, it is proposed to fill the identified gaps by theoretically substantiating influencer marketing models relevant to small businesses and by conducting an in-depth analysis of interaction practices that take into account digital trends and consumer behavior. Generalizing applied experience, adapting influencer selection criteria to the conditions of small businesses, and identifying barriers to scaling allow for the formation of a new methodological framework that will contribute to expanding the scientific understanding of the topic and developing practical strategies for the sustainable growth of small companies.

Formulation of the article's objectives (definition of tasks). The article aims to theoretically substantiate and empirically investigate strategic approaches to using influencer marketing as a tool for scaling small businesses, taking into account digital trends, consumer behavior, and the specifics of entrepreneurial resources.

Objectives of the article:

1. To study influencer marketing as an element of the digital marketing strategy of small businesses, identifying its functional features and specifics of application in various business models.
2. To assess the impact of key parameters of influencer selection on the effectiveness of marketing campaigns and to identify effective interaction models considering the stage of enterprise development and strategic goals.
3. To identify the main barriers to implementing influencer marketing in small businesses and develop practical recommendations for building an adaptive scaling strategy with an orientation towards sustainable development.

Presentation of the main research material. Influencer marketing, as a form of communication interaction between a brand and a target audience through opinion leaders, occupies an essential place in the modern digital strategies of small businesses. Unlike classic advertising channels, influencers can establish more authentic contact with subscribers, which increases trust in the promoted product and stimulates emotional engagement. The essence of influencer marketing is not only to convey information about the product but also to create a context in which the product or service is perceived as part of the lifestyle, values, or personal choice of the influencer himself. This form of marketing is transformed depending on the enterprise's business model, covering both direct promotion and co-authorship of content or the formation of brand communities. In small businesses, where limited resources do not allow for large-scale advertising campaigns, influencer marketing often serves as a targeted but effective tool for generating demand, particularly in social networks and niche markets (table 1).

Table 1

Forms of influencer marketing implementation depending on the business model of a small business

Type of small business model	Form of influencer marketing usage	Expected effect
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B2C (consumer goods)	Demonstration of a product in everyday use by an influencer, reviews, promotional codes	Raising awareness, stimulating quick sales
B2B (services or solutions for business)	Partner publications in specialized blogs, recommendations through experts	Strengthening trust, forming reputational capital
Creative industries (design, crafts)	Collaborations with influencers to create unique content	Expanding reach, emotional positioning of the brand
Online commerce	Series of stories, «unboxing» reviews, and live broadcasts with answers	Increasing engagement, increasing conversion
Local services type	Recommendations of local bloggers, geotargeted content	Formation of loyalty in the local market

Source: formed by the author based on [3, p. 43-44; 6; 10, p. 110-111]

The presented forms of implementation of influencer marketing demonstrate that its successful application in small businesses depends on the ability of the enterprise to integrate this tool into the overall communication strategy by the type of business model. In the case of B2C enterprises, the key is to reach a broad audience with maximum emotional engagement, which is achieved through native presentation formats - personal recommendations, reviews in stories, and «unpacking» of products [15]. Such techniques are especially effective in short sales funnels when the decision to purchase is made quickly. For the B2B segment, the priority is not the scale of coverage but the quality of trust: the influencer should not be just a popular person but an authoritative expert in a narrow industry [16]. His opinion is formed as proof of the effectiveness of the service or solution, which helps strengthen a small enterprise's business image [12, p. 339].

In creative industries, the need to create unique visual and semantic content dominates, where the influencer is involved as a co-author - a designer, artist, stylist or content maker - giving the brand a distinct identity. Online trading is focused on rapid lead generation, so serial communication in short videos, live, and interactives that provoke an audience reaction in real time is compelling. For local services

(coffee shops, salons, workshops), a recommendation from a regional micro-influencer is valuable, as it creates the effect of «one of their own» and inspires trust at the local community level. Thus, the differentiation of approaches to influencer marketing provides flexibility and relevance to small business communication, allowing you to minimize costs while maintaining high performance in a highly competitive digital environment.

The success of influencer marketing in small businesses largely depends on the correct choice of an opinion leader, who should not only have a particular popularity but also meet the enterprise's strategic objectives. The parameters by which an influencer is selected include audience characteristics, level of coverage, degree of audience involvement and relevance of content to the product or service. Ignoring at least one of these factors leads to an imbalance in the communication campaign: it can receive wide coverage without a real effect or, conversely, be meaningful but not noticeable in the information flow [10, p. 115]. For small businesses, which are limited in financial and organizational resources, errors in choosing an influencer are especially critical because the campaign is often one-time and does not provide a margin for correction. Therefore, an objective assessment of the main parameters of an influencer is the key to the effectiveness of cooperation (table 2).

In practice, these parameters function as a system of interdependent filters; the effectiveness of the entire marketing campaign depends on the accuracy of their settings. If the selected audience does not correspond to the target segment of a small business, even high-quality content and wide publication will not provide the expected conversions. The correspondence of the socio-demographic profile of the influencer's subscribers allows you to achieve an accurate hit on the interests of a potential client, which is especially important in conditions of a limited budget.

Table 2

Key parameters for choosing an influencer and their impact on the effectiveness of a small business marketing campaign

Influencer selection parameter	Content characteristic	Potential impact on a small business marketing campaign
Audience	Correspondence of the socio-demographic profile of subscribers to the brand's target audience	Increase in content relevance and conversion rate
Reach	Total number of users who see the influencer's content	Formation of brand awareness among a broader segment
Engagement	Subscriber activity in the form of likes, comments, and reposts	Determines the level of trust and depth of the message's impact
Relevance	Correspondence of the influencer's content topic to the brand's positioning	Increase the authenticity of communication and reduce the perception of advertising as intrusive

Source: formed by the author based on [6, 7, p. 208-209; 8]

As a quantitative characteristic, reach does not guarantee a result without qualitative engagement: with low subscriber activity, even high reach does not provide communicative depth. The engagement parameter is key to building trust in the brand and an emotional connection with the product. It is essential to monitor the level of likes and the ratio of comments, saves and re-views since they reflect the depth of interaction.

The relevance of content affects the perception of an advertising message. When promotion occurs within a familiar, thematically close context, the audience perceives the product as part of the usual information space and not as intrusive advertising. It significantly reduces the risks of reputational losses and strengthens the brand's authenticity.

Practical examples only reinforce this dependence: in particular, the Hoyra brand campaign in collaboration with Leonid Martynchyk was successful precisely due to the relevance of the content topic [17], and the EVA integration with Anna

Trincher achieved an effect due to the exact coincidence of audience characteristics and communication style [18]. Thus, for small businesses, the strategic selection of an influencer is not a question of popularity but a question of the exact combination of parameters that ensure meaningful and cost-effective communication.

The effectiveness of influencer marketing for small businesses largely depends on the ability to choose an appropriate interaction model that meets both the current stage of the enterprise's development and its marketing goals. In the initial phase, the business is usually focused on creating recognition and attracting the first audience and, therefore, requires tools with minimal costs and high emotional involvement. In the growth phase, the goals shift to building loyalty, strengthening the competitive position and scaling the market presence. At the mature stage, the emphasis is on maintaining the reputation, updating the image or introducing new products to already formed audiences. Considering these changes allows you to adapt the format of cooperation with influencers to a specific business task, making it possible to use influencer marketing not situationally but as an element of a long-term strategy (table 3).

In modern influencer marketing, the interaction models between small businesses and opinion leaders vary depending on the stage of development of the enterprise and marketing guidelines. At the start-up stage, companies often focus on narrowly targeted target audiences, choosing niche communicators with a moderate subscriber base but a high level of engagement instead of media stars, in the case of Genius. Space, this strategy - involving five opinion leaders from the fields of online education, psychology and business, who shared values with the brand - ensured high relevance of the contact. The campaign was adapted for each influencer, which allowed them to achieve 180% DKR (defining key results) in terms of the number of registrations, which indicates the effectiveness of the targeted approach at the development stage [19].

Table 3

Interaction models between small businesses and influencers depending on the stage of development and marketing goals

Stage of enterprise development	Marketing goal	Recommended model of interaction with influencers	Expected effect
Start-up stage	Creating initial brand recognition	Barter or partnership cooperation with micro-influencers	Low budget, emotional engagement and first leads
Active growth phase	Scaling the audience, increasing sales	Paid cooperation with thematically relevant mid-level influencers	Forecasted conversion, growth in traffic and customer base
Stabilization / maturity phase	Strengthening market position, maintaining loyalty	Long-term ambassador programs, attracting opinion leaders	Sustainable reach, reputational stability, repeat purchases
Refreshment or change phase	Rebranding, launching a new product line	Creative integration with niche or multi-genre influencers	Restimulation of interest in the brand, attracting new segments
Regional expansion phase	Entering new markets or cities	Geotargeted cooperation with local bloggers	Adaptation to the local context, reducing the barrier to entry

Source: formed by the author based on [4, p. 71-72; 5; 12, p. 141-143]

In contrast, in the scaling phase, brands emphasize coverage and image integration. In the Atlantic Group case study, featured in MMR.ua, a paid collaboration with popular influencer Ramina Eshakzai included a series of personalized video reviews and live sessions with brand representatives, which allowed to announce a new clothing collection and build emotionally engaged communication. The campaign led to a 38% increase in orders in the first four weeks and a 20 % increase in brand subscribers, emphasizing reputation-verified cooperation's effectiveness in mature business models [20].

The strategic implementation of influencer marketing in small businesses is accompanied by several systemic problems and barriers that reduce the effectiveness of communication interaction and limit the scaling of digital campaigns. The main

challenge is the insufficient analytical readiness of small businesses to identify relevant influencers who match the brand's value base and the target audience's characteristics. Due to the lack of specialized internal marketing teams or external partner contractors, small businesses often find themselves choosing influencers based on subjective criteria (visual perception of the profile, number of followers), ignoring the level of engagement, authenticity of content, and audience trust indicators [7, p. 206].

A significant problem remains the asymmetry of expectations between businesses and influencers regarding interaction formats, partnership terms, and DKRs. The idea of guaranteed performance often dominates small businesses after a one-time integration, which contradicts the nature of the long-term effect of reputation marketing. In addition, due to limited budgets, companies try to implement campaigns without financial compensation for influencers, which complicates communication and reduces interest in quality content [5]. Existing barter or free models without legal agreements create risks of non-compliance with agreements or misuse of content. A separate barrier is distrust of digital metrics or misunderstanding of the mechanisms for their interpretation. The lack of access to full-fledged analytical systems does not allow small businesses to assess the effectiveness of collaboration based on data on reach, traffic, click-through rate or conversion [12, p. 181]. It leads to erroneous conclusions about the ineffectiveness of influencer marketing and reduces the willingness to reuse such strategies in the future.

No less critical is the problem of the lack of adapted instructions or templates for implementing influencer campaigns that would take into account the limited resources of small businesses [6]. The lack of educational programs on digital marketing in the local business environment reduces the ability of business owners or managers to develop effective communication models. In conditions of

information overload and high competition, even potentially valuable collaboration with an influencer can go unnoticed without professional training for promotion.

An adaptive influencer marketing strategy for small businesses should consider resource constraints, the dynamism of the digital environment, and the need to build a presence in the market gradually. To ensure sustainable development and scaling, it is first necessary to form a clear system of goals that combines short-term results (increasing reach and recognition) with long-term effects, such as forming a loyal audience, increasing conversions, and reputational capital. The basis of an effective strategy should be the segmentation of influencers not only by quantitative criteria (macro, micro, nano) but also by thematic profile, value compatibility, and quality of interaction with the audience.

In an unstable market, small companies should implement a phased interaction model, where niche opinion leaders with high involvement are used at the initial level. As they scale up, they are supplemented with collaborations with more powerful influencers who can strengthen the brand in the broader information field. This approach allows the marketing budget to be allocated more effectively and constantly tests the target audience's response without excessive risk.

It is essential to create a standardized interaction system: a brief template, a code of ethics for cooperation, a content management policy and feedback mechanisms, which allows you to institutionalize the practice of influencer marketing within the company. It, in turn, contributes to the transition from chaotic one-time campaigns to the sustainable formation of a communication ecosystem based on partnership and reputational trust.

A key element of adaptability is using analytics as a basis for decision-making. Small businesses should focus on available tools (Google Analytics, Meta Insights, specialized mention monitoring platforms) to constantly measure campaign effectiveness, adjust parameters, and select the most relevant content formats and time placement. At the same time, it is advisable to create your DKRs - for example,

the cost of attracting one subscriber through an influencer or the level of audience retention after a campaign - which allows you to compare results over different periods.

Taking into account the requirements of sustainable development, special attention should be paid to the principle of authenticity: not to obsessive promotion, but to involving in communication those influencers who already share ideas close to the mission of small businesses (environmental friendliness, locality, responsible consumption). It provides a higher level of audience trust and reduces the need for high fees since the motivation for cooperation is formed from ideological, not just financial considerations.

As a result, an adaptive influencer marketing strategy for small businesses should be based on the gradual building of long-term partnerships, precise analytical control, contextualized selection of thought leaders and synchronization with the brand's value platform. This approach increases the effectiveness of not only individual campaigns but also the overall digital strategy of the enterprise, opening up the prospect of scalable growth in conditions of changing market dynamics.

Conclusions. The study found that influencer marketing is a promising tool for the strategic development of small businesses, especially in conditions of digitalization. Its effectiveness depends on the stage of enterprise development, clear definition of goals, selection of relevant influencers and building flexible cooperation models. The main barriers to implementation were identified, particularly the opacity of metrics, complexity of assessing effectiveness, lack of planning, risks of reputational losses and tone of voice mismatch.

Practice shows that the most effective models are those based on value alignment and an analytical approach to partner selection. Further research should be aimed at integrating influencer marketing with other digital promotion tools, developing methodologies for assessing its effectiveness for SMEs and forming ethical and legal principles for cooperation.

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